

ISic0092

Honours for Caius Maesius

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2018-07-10 (Prag)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 116

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. C(aio) · Maesio · Aquillio
2. Fabio Titiano · c(larissimo) · v(iro) · co(n)s(uli)
3. optimo civi ac patrono beneme
4. renti ordo et populus splen
5. [d]idissimae col(oniae) Aug(ustae) Himereorum
6. [The]rmit(anorum) pecunia sua posuit

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

To Gaius Maesius Aquillius Fabius Titianus, a man of most illustrious fame (i.e. of senatorial class), most excellent consul, citizen and patron. The council and people of the most splendid Colonia Augusta Himereorum Thermitanorum erected this at their own expense to the well-deserving man.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285283

EDR 127504

EDCS 22100046

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7345 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650796>)

Bivona, L. 1994. *Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica.* Palermo / Rome. At 9

Manganaro, G. 1982. I senatori di Sicilia e il problema del latifondo. *Atti del Colloquio Internazionale AIEGL, su "epigrafia ed ordine senatorio", Roma 14-20/5/81.* Roma. pp. 369-385. At 375

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW.* 2.11.1: 3-89. At 79

Amata, G.M. 2015. Alcune considerazioni sull'epigrafe onoraria CIL X 7345 dalla colonia di Augusta Himereorum Thermitanorum.

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0092. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334099>

Photo J. Prag, courtesy Museo Civico Baldassare Romano